

Preparedness, availability, and usage of Information Communication Technology among college pre-service teachers during teaching practice exercises

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Abstract

The study investigated ICT skill preparedness, availability of ICT infrastructure and resources, and the usage of ICT skills by pre-service teachers in secondary schools for internships in Delta State. The study used a descriptive survey design and a structured questionnaire to collect data. 120 student-teachers were randomly selected from 10 schools, using a stratified sampling method, from the list of schools that posted students. Three research questions were raised and answered by using descriptive statistics. A test of significance was done using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The study found low levels of technological preparedness with an overall mean of 2.05, a low level of available ICT facilities and resources with an overall mean of 1.92, a low level of usage of ICT with an overall mean of 1.80, as well as a weak positive relationship between preparedness and usage of technology. The study recommends modifying teaching strategies of teacher educators to include ICT, funding of schools with ICT facilities by the government, and the compulsory utilization of ICT resources in the lesson delivery process at all levels of the educational system.

Keywords: Preparedness, Availability, Usage, ICT, pre-service teachers

Introduction

Teaching processes in this twenty-first century have changed and require teachers to be able to add technology resources in their lessons to meet the present-day requirements for the ability to read and write (Kong et al., 2014). It becomes extremely important for new teachers to integrate technology into their teaching right away when they are in the field of practice through digital whiteboards, using students' smartphones or other devices for learning during class time.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is made up of computers, the internet, and electronic delivery systems such as radios, televisions, and projectors, which are used extensively in the education sector. ICT is increasingly being applied in instruction, learning, and assessment. It is also considered a powerful tool for educational change and reform. Some research findings have shown that appropriate use of ICT can improve educational quality and connect learning to real-life situations (Lowther et al., 2008; Weert & Tatnall, 2005). Recent research has pointed out that ICT assists in transforming a teaching environment into a learner-centered one (Castro Sanchez & Aleman, 2011). It provides anytime access to the learners and the teachers to enhance the updated knowledge. It gives hope for the development of individuals and society (Kumari & Naaz, 2012). If a teacher has the skill to use ICT devices appropriately, she can easily use teaching-learning materials based on ICT like multimedia PowerPoints, videos, etc. (Player-Koro, 2012)

The introduction of digital technologies into the education system and the pervasive use of information in the education system and teaching with technologies are unavoidable for all teachers at all levels. Teacher Education programs prepare teachers to use their students' technologies at home and out of home for knowledge gathering and dissemination. When technology is systematically selected and utilized, it has the potential to promote and propagate effective teaching and learning practices that accelerate and expand the effect of learning principles as reported by the U.S. Department of Education (2017). ICT has experienced significant progress in recent times, and efforts have been made to modernize the teaching of Science using ICT, especially in secondary schools, which is a significant level of formal education between the primary and higher levels of education. Since ICT is famous as a tool that has transformed the global education system, as well as helped educators all over the world achieve their learning objectives, it is strongly recommended to be used in the delivery of science instruction (Olafare, Lawrence, and Fakorede, 2017). ICT-based teaching-learning process was important during the COVID-19 pandemic which was not easy for teachers and students.

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Pre-service science teachers are students in science education programs at tertiary institutions, that are being prepared with the knowledge, skills, as well as attitudes essential for teaching in primary and secondary schools. This training confirms their readiness for the profession. According to the sixth edition of the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2013), all teachers must have appropriate qualifications, and training programs should include essential components such as Information Technology. Consequently, most teacher education programs worldwide now incorporate technology training, leading to the characterization of today's pre-service teachers as "digital natives," reflecting their upbringing in a technological environment (Batane and Ngwako, 2017).

Teaching practice is the first opportunity for many pre-service teachers to practice the skills they obtained during the coursework of their programs; a place where the would-be teachers first demonstrate their teaching philosophies and practices. It is therefore worth discovering whether technology use would be part of the teachers' set of skills right from the beginning of their teaching activity.

Efficient use of ICT requires a good and conducive environment in secondary and tertiary science classrooms (Jack and Songo, 2020) which is achieved by the provision of sufficient quantities of new technological gadgets, science teachers, and ICT skill acquisition. Science teachers need to meet the curriculum standard of technological skills to effectively integrate technology into the classroom. While inappropriate use of technology can hinder learning, promotion of learning can be by the application of an appropriate ICT resource for a given learning objective. According to Nagel (2013), challenges of teaching with ICT include career advancement, resistance to change, massive open online courses, delivery of informal learning, failure of personalized learning, and failure to use technology to deliver effective formative assessment. Husain (2011) identified the present position of ICT and pre-service teacher education among others include being taught only about technology, only the basics of computers taught to student teachers, and the knowledge of student teachers on ICT application in teaching is limited mainly to computer literacy. Major barriers to teaching with ICT as stipulated by Habibu AI Mamun and Clement (2012) include the need for genuine software, insufficient computers in the classroom, low-speed internet, deficient motivation among teachers and students to make use of ICT, lack of suitable training skills, unavailability of latest ICT equipment, lack of expert technological staff, poor administrative support, and poor curriculum. In the study by Amuko et al., (2015) the barriers were identified as school-related problems which include the provision of ICT hardware and software, for example, desktops/laptops, projectors, interactive whiteboards, internet services, and others. Limited resources such as subject-specific software, computers and multimedia projectors, interactive whiteboards, e-learning facilities, and broadband internet access, as identified by Bello et al., (2017), are inadequate in teacher education institutions and could result in a lack of access to pre-service teachers.

Iderima and Agwu (2020) in a similar study observed that student-teachers showed readiness to teach with ICT because they possessed the basic technological skills, attitude, and efficiency for teaching with ICT. They also showed a good level of readiness to integrate technology into their teaching as long as the necessary ICT infrastructure is provided.

Numerous researches have concentrated on the integration as well as the role of ICT in the teaching and learning process (Joshi, 2017; Kayshap et al., 2021). Other studies examined the competency and use of ICT hardware and software by preservice teachers in other states of Nigeria (Bitok, 2014; Egunjobi, 2015; Jack, 2021; Timothy et al., 2022); there is a paucity of research on the level of use of ICT among preservice science teachers during a teaching practice exercise in Nigeria.

The introduction and usage of ICT in teaching and learning are met with challenges that hinder the spread of ICT in different schools, even teacher education institutions, hence hindering the use of ICT by pre-service teachers. Although ICT is part of the curriculum for teacher education, there have been reports of inadequate provision of the ICT infrastructure and digital learning materials, hence, Science education lessons delivery have been known to go on without technology. Pre-service teachers' knowledge, competence, and use of ICT during their teaching practicum could be influenced by these factors.

Aim and objectives

The study aims to investigate the level of utilization of ICT among pre-service teachers of the Colleges of Education in Delta State during their teaching practice exercise. The study will use the following objectives to guide the study:

1. To determine the extent of the pre-service teachers' knowledge of technological skills
2. To ascertain the availability of ICT resources in the schools where the pre-service teachers are posted.
3. To determine the frequency of use of ICT by pre-service teachers during lesson delivery

Research Questions

1. How prepared are pre-service teachers to use ICT in teaching?
2. Are there available ICT infrastructural facilities and digital learning resources in the school of teaching internship?
3. What is the level of use of ICT during instruction delivery?

Hypothesis

There is no relationship between the level of technological skills (level of preparedness) and the frequency of utilization (level of use) of ICT by pre-service teachers

Methodology

A descriptive survey research design was chosen for this study. The population was made up of all pre-service science teachers from the two Colleges of Education in Delta State. A list of the schools where pre-service teachers had placements was procured from the Teaching Practice unit of the Curriculum and Instruction Department of the Delta State College of Education, Mosogar, which was selected by ballot between the two Colleges of Education in Delta State. A stratified sampling method was used to select the schools to ensure adequate representation and got a total of 10 schools. A sample size of 120 pre-service teachers, who had taken the courses: GSE011 (Media and Information Literacy I), GSE021 (Media and Information Literacy II), GSE213 (Introduction to Computer Studies), and EDU213 (Educational Technology: Theory and Practice) in the 2021/2022 academic session. were picked randomly.

The instrument used for the study was a structured questionnaire called Pre-service Teachers Level of Usage of ICT (PTLUICT) with a 4-point Likert scale (having Strongly disagree, disagree, Agree, and Strongly agree responses with numerical values of 1, 2, 3, and 4 respectively), that was developed by the researcher, was used for collecting data. The questionnaire had three (3) sections of 5 items per section with section 1 – Level of preparedness with technological skills, section 2 – Level of usage of ICT by pre-service teachers, and section 3 – Availability of ICT resources in the school of teaching practice.

Face and content validity were determined by experts in Educational Technology and experts in Measurement and Evaluation of the School of Education in Delta State College of Education, Mosogar. The test-retest method was done with pre-service teachers from the College of Education Warri to determine the instrument's reliability.

The researcher visited the selected schools and after asking for consent from the School Principal to conduct the study, pre-service teachers assigned to the school were informed of the purpose of the study and their anonymity in attending to the questionnaire items was assured. Only those who gave their consent were given the instrument to fill out. The researcher collected the completed instruments as soon as they were completed.

Descriptive statistics using SPSS version 16.0 were used to analyze the responses. Mean and standard deviation were utilized to answer the research questions while the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient to test the hypothesis.

Results

Research Question 1: How prepared are pre-service teachers to use ICT in teaching?

Table 1: Descriptive statistics showing the extent of preparedness to use ICT during Teaching

S/N	STATEMENT OF ITEM	N	MEAN	SD	LEVEL
1.	I was adequately taught using ICT resources	120	2.31	0.15	Low
2.	I know how to gather appropriate learning resources	120	1.50	0.23	Low
3.	I know search engines to prepare my lessons	120	3.10	0.21	High
4.	I can identify resources that meet nearly all the criteria	120	2.14	0.18	Low
5.	I have respect for the legal and ethical rights of information use	120	1.22	0.20	Low
Overall Mean			2.05		Low

Key: ≥ 3.00 = High; 2.99 – 2.50 = Moderate; ≤ 2.49 = Low

Table 1 shows the mean responses for the five items on the level of preparedness of pre-service teachers to teaching with ICT with the range of 1.22 – 3.10 and an overall mean response of 2.05 which represents a low level of preparedness of the pre-service science teachers to teaching with ICT. All responses to the items were low except item number 3 which indicated that the teachers had a high level of knowledge of search engines to prepare lessons.

Research Question 2: Are there available ICT infrastructural facilities and digital learning resources in the school of teaching internship?

Table 2: Descriptive statistics showing the responses to the availability of ICT resources

S/N	STATEMENT OF ITEM	N	MEAN	SD	LEVEL
1.	Internet services	120	2.20	0.16	Low
2.	Projector and whiteboard	120	1.30	0.20	Low
3.	Flash disk/CD-Rom	120	2.30	1.47	Low
4.	Computers (Desktop/Laptops)	120	3.30	1.10	High
5.	e-books	120	0.50	0.34	Low
Overall Mean			1.92		Low

Key: ≥ 3.00 = High; 2.99 – 2.50 = Moderate; ≤ 2.49 = Low

The results in Table 2 revealed an overall mean of 1.92 which indicated a low availability of ICT resources. Computers (desktops/laptops) had the highest mean responses which indicated they are available in the schools and the least available ICT resource were e-books with a mean of 0.50. Internet services had a low mean response of 2.20, which indicated a low level of availability in addition to flash disks/CD-ROM, and Projectors and whiteboards which had mean responses of 2.30 and 1.30 respectively.

Research Question 3: What is the level of use of ICT during instruction delivery?

Table 3: Descriptive statistics showing the responses on the level of use of ICT by pre-service teachers

S/N	STATEMENT OF ITEM	N	MEAN	SD	LEVEL
1.	I can turn on and turn off a computer	120	2.80	0.38	Moderate
2.	I use whiteboard/projectors in teaching my lessons	120	0.30	0.20	Low
3.	I use e-learning resources for the preparation of my lessons	120	2.30	0.45	Low
4.	I store students' score records on a flash disk	120	1.50	0.32	Low
5.	I make use of YouTube videos during the teaching-learning process with my Android phone	120	2.60	0.50	Moderate
Overall Mean			1.80		Low

Key: ≥ 3.00 = High; 2.99 – 2.50 = Moderate; ≤ 2.49 = Low

Table 3 revealed that pre-service teachers moderately use social media handles like YouTube during lesson delivery by the use of their Android phones which showed a mean response of 2.6 and also possess moderate technological skills of the ability to turn on and off a computer system. Other items like the use of a whiteboard were low (0.30), in addition to the preparation of lessons with the use of e-learning and the storage of students' scores in flash disks with a mean response of 2.30 and 1.50 respectively.

Null Hypothesis: There is no relationship between the level of technological skills (level of preparedness) and the frequency of utilization (level of usage) of ICT by pre-service teachers

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient analysis revealed a low positive relationship of $r = 0.30$ between the level of preparedness of pre-service teachers with technological skills and their usage of ICT.

Discussion

The pre-service science teachers were observed to have a low level of preparedness to teach with ICT as shown by the overall mean response of 2.05. This may be because tertiary science education students are still being exposed to the analog ways of teaching and neglecting current innovations in the use of technologies in classroom lesson deliveries. This is not in accord with the study of Iderima and Agwu (2020) who reported a moderate level of preparedness for teaching with ICT. Batane and Ngwako (2017) reported that the non-expectancy to use ICT by student-teachers was made necessary by the fact that their trainers did not use ICT in their lesson delivery. It has been shown that a combination of theory and hands-on laboratory sessions has a significant effect on increasing technological knowledge (Wilson et al., 2020). Hence teachers who are more familiar with ICT and have higher levels of initial technological knowledge and ICT self-efficacy will use it to a greater extent in teaching and learning.

An overall low mean response of 1.92 was observed on the available ICT resources in the schools. Most of the schools did not have desktops/laptops or projectors except the Principal's office in some schools. This agrees with the findings of Jack (2021) who reported limited ICT resources and infrastructure in their study. Jack and Songo (2020) categorized inadequate provision of ICT as a school-related challenge, and by inference, contributes adversely to the effective use of ICT resources in secondary schools which can hinder the learning process. This result could be attributed to the rural location of the schools which according to Okwor (2011) opined that there are incidences of digital divide in Nigeria looking at different perspectives on a geographic ICT divide that results in unequal distribution among and between states and their urban commercial and cultural centers, between urban and rural areas (which is the most noticeable of the geographical ICT divides).

A positively low-strength relationship exists between the level of preparedness with ICT skills and the usage of ICT resources in the teaching-learning process. This result implies that there may be some usage of ICT in classrooms even though the level of preparedness of the student-teacher may not be adequate. The finding is in accord with that of Bitok (2014), Egunjobi (2015), and Jack (2021). Pre-service teachers are conversant with the use of ICT for other activities apart from school work which may influence their lesson preparation and delivery.

Conclusion

Teaching without the use of ICT in the classroom can hurt the learning process in the classroom. There is a low level of knowledge of technological skills by the pre-service teachers of the Colleges of Education in Delta State which implies a low level of preparedness. There is a low level of availability of ICT infrastructure and e-learning sources in the secondary schools where pre-service teachers carry out their teaching practice exercises. A low level of usage of ICT was also observed which was a consequence of non-available ICT resources in the schools. The study also observed a relationship between the level of preparedness with technological skills and the utilization of ICT for lesson delivery by the pre-service teachers.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this research, the under listed are the recommendations:

1. To overcome the limited level of ICT preparedness of student teachers, in-service teacher educators must be seen to change the traditional teacher education program by adequately using ICT in preparation and lesson delivery in tertiary institutions.
2. The government should support funding the procurement of ICT infrastructure and resources in secondary schools.
3. The use of ICT materials during instruction delivery and learning process should be made mandatory at all levels of our educational system.

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